

INCREASING LEAF PRODUCTIVITY BY GRAVING
MULBERRY TREES

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Annotation: *In the conditions of our republic, one-headed mulberry trees planted in rows and neglected mulberry groves can be found in large numbers. In order to increase their productivity, close to each other in the branches, withered branches and dried branches, small (bachki) branches are cut to the body, and leafy branches are given to worms. As a result, the main branches are full of strength, light and air pass to the branches better, the yield of leaves increases and its level of nutrition increases. At the same time, the shape of the tree branches is also changed. If the mulberries are single-headed, they are given a multi-headed form. For this purpose, three of the strongly grown branches are cut 40-50 cm long, and all other branches are cut from the base..*

Key words: *cocooning, mulberry, branch, twig, leaf, food, rejuvenation, productivity, external environmental factors, nutrition vegetation period.*

INTRODUCTION. In the world's leading countries where cocooning is developed, scientific researches are being conducted to create mulberry bush and semi-bush varieties adapted to large-leaved, moderate and extreme climatic conditions, and to establish productive mulberry groves based on them, using the genetic resources of mulberry and advanced molecular-genetic selection methods. As a result of scientific work in this direction, based on mulberry varieties rich in organic and mineral compounds necessary for mulberry silkworms, it is possible to care for silkworms several times a year, and it is possible to grow abundant cocoon raw materials with high quality indicators..

In our republic today, extensive measures are being taken to develop cocoon breeding, especially to create new mulberry varieties suitable for silkworm hybrids. At the same time, it is necessary to improve the productivity of mulberry varieties, research the mechanisms of influence of newly created mulberry varieties on the cocoon productivity and postembryonic viability of mulberry silkworm industrial hybrids, and further develop scientific research and innovative technologies to increase their effectiveness. In the strategy of Actions for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, special attention is paid to the development of agriculture,

especially livestock, including silk farming. In this regard, it is important to conduct scientific research on strengthening the nutritional base of the mulberry silkworm in the field of cocooning and mulberry production, that is, creating new varieties with high productivity, nutritious and nutritious properties and introducing them into production.

During the years of independence in our country, by creating and introducing new large-cocooned breeds and hybrids of mulberry silkworms, the yield of cocoons from one box of worms was increased to 57.0 kg. By 2018, more than 18,000 tons of live cocoons were grown. At the same time, insufficient attention has been paid to research on the propagation of the mulberry tree, which is the sole food base of the mulberry silkworm..

In this regard, paragraph 5 of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 12, 2018 "On measures for the further development of the silk industry of the Republic" No. given.

The level of study of the problem. A number of foreign authors G.B.Mulev, A.I.Kovalik (1977), M.Filkov (1958), A.Guldatov (1997) on breeding mulberry trees on a global scale and increasing leaf productivity, improving resistance to diseases and cold. based experiments were carried out..

Also, D.A. Komissarov (1938), N.P. Krenke (1950) in the creation of new varieties and hybrids of mulberry trees suitable for different climatic conditions of our Republic, on breeding from ringed, ringless, leafy, leafless cuttings of mulberry trees, improving the fertility and productivity of selection material), M.I. Deza (1951), K. Rahmonberdiev (1951), R. Kh. Turetsskaya (1961), S. Ostrouxova and P. Khojaevlar (1975-1980), O'. Kochkarov (1984), M. Hibbimov (2000), and S.T. Valievlar (2014) have conducted extensive scientific research.

Establishing productive mulberry plantations in our country for the cultivation of high-quality and abundant cocoons, creating new mulberry varieties that produce high-quality and nutritious leaves, and gradually introducing them to production, and proving the superiority of local mulberry varieties over the mulberry varieties currently brought from the People's Republic of China, is one of the urgent issues of today. is counted.

In our republic, one of the urgent issues in the propagation of mulberry trees from cuttings is to increase the speed of rooting, swelling, water absorption, and leaf productivity of new and fogged varieties of mulberry from cuttings for grafting and to obtain leaf yield in a short period of time.

In our republic, mulberries are distinguished from perennial trees by the fact that their leafy branches are completely cut off once and sometimes even two or three times per season. In this regard, as a result of improper pruning, poor care, and improper cutting of branches, mulberry grows weakly, the leaves crumble, the level of nutrition decreases, and the yield decreases. Due to the cutting of the branches in the head for the worm, the new ones grow very densely, and next year the shoots in their lower half will not spread. And the leaves formed in the middle part do not get enough sunlight,

as a result, the yield of such mulberries also decreases, and their nutritional value decreases.

In the conditions of our republic, such phenomena can be found especially in single-headed mulberry trees planted in rows and neglected mulberry groves. In order to increase their productivity, close to each other in the branches, withered branches and dried branches, small (bachki) branches are cut to the body, and leafy branches are given to worms. As a result, the main branches are full of strength, light and air pass to the branches better, the yield of leaves increases and its level of nutrition increases. At the same time, the shape of the tree branches is also changed. If the mulberries are single-headed, they are given a multi-headed form. For this purpose, three of the 40-50 cm long branches of the mulberry tree are placed opposite to each other during the feeding of the bollworm, and all other branches are cut from the base. Next year, during the feeding period of the bollworm, two 30-40 cm branches are left on each of the three branches, and the upper part is cut. At the same time, all the branches coming out of the head and its base are cut to the body. In subsequent years, the branches are cut in the same way. Such mulberries have two-tiered and six-headed branches. After the branches of the mulberry bush are cleaned of dead branches and dead branches, three to four strong branches of each bush are cut at a height of 50 cm, and the branches in their lower part are cut close to the body. Among the trees planted in rows, there are many mulberries with bulging heads, thickened and rotting. Such a phenomenon is more common in single-headed mulberry trees that have not been shaped into branches.

Their branches grow poorly and produce very few leaves. To restore the yield of such mulberries, it is necessary to cut the swollen or rotten part of the head, that is, to rejuvenate the tree. The work of rejuvenating trees should be carried out before the movement of aphids in the plant (from the second day of February to the middle of March). The advantage of rejuvenation in these periods. Bakirov and Yu. It was also confirmed in Migalimov's experiments. Rejuvenation works are carried out as follows. The swelling of single-headed mulberries is cut from the base with a sharp saw. It is recommended not to cut all the heads of multi-headed mulberries at once, but to cut them alternately (that is, the most swollen head in the first year, the rest in the following years). Then the branches are less damaged..

The leaf yield can be increased by rejuvenating old tall and bushy mulberry trees planted in mulberry fields that have failed due to lack of maintenance. Tall mulberry trees in a mulberry grove are rejuvenated like trees planted in rows. Among them, if the body has dried up to the lower part, it is cut off leaving 2-3 cm, and a new body and multi-headed shape is given.

Bush mulberries are cut 1-2 cm above the root neck. The incision should be as perpendicular to the body as possible, so that its surface is smaller and heals faster. So that the juice does not overflow from the cut place of the mulberry and does not get sick, it is immediately poured with garden zamazak, kraska or mud mixed with manure. On a rejuvenated single-headed tall mulberry tree, three strong branches of 50 cm are

left, and everything that grows around the cut is cut from the base of other branches. In the third year of growth, during worm feeding, two in each of the three heads, a total of six branches 30 cm high, are left, and the branches that come out from under it are cut short.

If the tree is three-headed during rejuvenation, in the second year, two strong branches of each head are left 30 cm, and the rest are cut close to the body. A single-headed mulberry rejuvenated in this way will be given a two-tiered and six-headed form in the third year, and a three-headed mulberry in the second year. In the following years, the mulberry branches are cut with the heads left for the worm.

In rejuvenated bush mulberries, during the second year, during the feeding of the bollworm, three to four of the branches that grew last year are cut at a height of 50 cm, and the rest are cut from the base. In the third and subsequent years, the branches from three or four heads left behind are cut. U. According to Bakirov, under production conditions, the leaf yield and productivity (cocoon grown per 1 ha) increased by 2.1-2.4 times when rejuvenating old mulberry bushes left over from the harvest.

When rejuvenating measures were carried out simultaneously with deep plowing (28-30 cm) between the rows, the productivity increased by 1.5-1.9 times. In order to produce new branches and increase leaf yield in rejuvenated mulberry trees, it is recommended to apply 120-180 kg of nitrogen, 60-90 kg of phosphorus and 5-10 tons of fertilizer to each mulberry tree. This experiment fully confirms the results of the author's scientific research on the same issue. M.I. Grebinskaya (1962) recommends grafting young bush mulberries between the bark and cuttings of productive mulberries.

For this purpose, the lower part of a mulberry cutting with 2-3 joints is cut on one side at a 35 degree angle from the opposite side to the bud, and the bark on the opposite side of the cut is scraped a little (until it turns green). Then the lower part of the pen is inserted between the wood and the bark of the cut of the rejuvenated mulberry. In this case, the bark part of the pen should be placed on the wood of the graft, and the wood part should be placed on the bark. After that, only the upper shoot of the pen is left partially open, and the lower one is completely buried with soil.

A week before grafting and 7-10 days after grafting, mulberries are watered. When the grafted branches reach 12-15 cm, the branches from the graft are removed. If grafting does not take place, two branches are left, and three of them are grafted again next year. When the height of the joints is 1 m, their circumference is softened. The bottoms are buried with soil.

In the first year of growth, only phosphorus and potassium fertilizers are given at the rate of 30 kg per hectare in August of the first growth year, and nitrogen fertilizers are applied in the second year, so that the grafts do not rot and ripen well. Using the leaves of such mulberries next year, when the worm is 4-5 years old, the branches are cut at a height of 50 cm above the ground level. According to the recommendation of O. Polatov, if the low-yielding khasha is grafted to the branches of 5-6-year-old trees

between the cutting and the bark, the bud will grow stronger than the graft, and the yield of leaves will be 1.5-2 times more.

Branches of the graft are cut obliquely, a pencil is placed on the upper part of the cut, and cotton soaked in a light solution of potassium permanganate is placed to cover the cut. Then it is wrapped with a polyethylene film, paper is placed on it, and the hemp is tied, leaving only the upper shoot of the pen open. After 4-5 leaves are produced in the pen, the film is removed and re-wrapped only with paper, after 1-2 months the paper is also removed.

Table 1
Rejuvenation of mulberries left over from perennial crops by grafting and increasing their productivity.

It was carried out in the spring of 2021 in the territory of Agrotexservis, Beshariq district, Fergana region..

Welding methods	The number of grafts planted			The average length of a one-year branch, cm
	Total	He was bruised from that		
		piece	%	
Grafting under the bark of high-bodied Tajikistan seedless mulberry variety.	400	320	80	110
Bushy Grafting under the bark of the mulberry variety.	400	300	75	100
Pioner, grafting of the mulberry variety.	400	290	72,5	95
Cukoso-70, tube grafting of mulberry variety..	400	220	55	70
	400	230	57,5	72

Hasaki mulberry variety (control)				
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A total of 400 mulberry cuttings were grafted under the bark to rejuvenate the Tajik seedless mulberry variety, of which 320 sprouted. That is, it is 80%. As a result of the research, the average length of the one-year variety is 110 cm. A total of 400 mulberry cuttings were grafted under the bark to rejuvenate the bushy Jarariq mulberry, 300 of which turned green. That is, it is 75%. As a result of the research, the average length of the one-year variety is 100 cm. A total of 400 mulberry bushes were grafted to rejuvenate the high-bodied Kukoso-70 mulberry variety, of which 220 sprouted. That is, it is 55%. As a result of the research, the average length of the variety during the one-year vegetation period was 70 cm. When 400 mulberry cuttings were grafted to rejuvenate bushy Pioneer mulberries, 290 of them turned green. That is, it is 72.5%. As a result of the research, the average length of the variety during the one-year vegetation period is 95 cm..

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